

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on **Milestone 27**

Draft report on the impact of the GDPR on research and the EOSC

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Abstract:

SSHOC Milestone 27 refers to the preparation of a draft report on the impact of the GDPR on research and EOSC. The team has described and compared national implementations of the GDPR, with focus on some specific countries, and prepared the draft report as planned in M14 of the project. The actual draft report is attached as an Annex to this Milestone report.

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1. Introduction

The GDPR has given European countries a unique opportunity to harmonize their legal framework, and to improve the conditions for research and cross-border data flow. The rationale behind the new regulation is to ensure the same level of data protection throughout the EU in order to facilitate open access and reusability of research data. Thus, the GDPR has a limited flexibility in its application. Nevertheless, the Regulation leaves room for national supplementary provisions, including derogations, and this possibility applies especially to the field of research. This represents both risks and opportunities. The draft report that the Task 5.3 of the SSHOC project is preparing describes and compares national implementation of the GDPR with the focus on research in some specific countries: Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany and Italy.

The draft report has compared the national data protection legislations and analysed whether or not they are beneficial for research and archival purposes.

2. Description of the Milestone

Task 5.3 addresses legal issues related to open access, reusability of research data, and legal implementation of the FAIR principles. Focus will be on the implementation of the GDPR and its implications for cross-border research in Europe. The task will also initiate the creation of an SSH GDPR Code of Conduct to be handed over to and finalised in T8.3 Legal and Ethical Issues

One of the teams in this task will describe, analyse and compare national implementation of the GDPR in relation to research. The aim is to identify if and how national variations may impose legal barriers to the accessing and reusability of research data within the context of EOSC. Focus will be on research derogations and national supplementary provisions, and the extent to which they support open access and reusability or reinforce existing legal barriers and restrictive data sharing practices.

This milestone achieved was to draft a report on the implementation of the GDPR in relation to research (Country report).

2.1. Role of the Milestone

Work on this milestone has laid ground for further work in task 5.3, as the task has a good starting point to further explore how the GDPR has been implemented in different European countries. Going further with the work the task will add data from more countries and will conduct interviews with researchers in order to get first-hand knowledge on how GDPR has affected cross-border research.

2.2. Means of verification

According to the Grant Agreement GA, table 1.3.4 WT4 List of Milestones the means of verification for this milestone is that "Draft report is available". The draft report is finished, however at this point the report is a draft and it will not be made available at Zenodo. The report will be made openly available at Zenodo when finalised as a Deliverable in M21 of the project. As for now the draft report is provided as an Annex to this Milestone report.

Conclusions and next steps

The work the task has done in this report/milestone has been important to be able to move forward with the work in the task and as a basis for a future deliverable.

For the tasks next deliverables and milestones, the team will continue expanding the findings of this report, including data from other countries and supplementing them with interviews from researchers in the field

The work in task 5.3 is moving forward as planned.

Annexes

Annex 1: Country report MS27.

Annex 1: *Country Report draft*

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Social Sciences & Humanities **Open Cloud**

Project Number: 823782

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Duration: 40 months

Country Report (draft)

Dissemination Level	PU
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Abstract:

In this report, the team has described and compared national implementations of the GDPR, with focus on some specific countries: Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany and Italy. This report has compared national data protection legislation and analysed whether or not they are beneficial for research and archival purposes.

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History

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0.6	27.02.2020	5th draft, editing and comments	Lea Haahr
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Executive Summary

This report is the first milestone of task 5.3 in SSHOC, called Legal Issues of innovative data access. In this report the team has compared the national data protection legislations in some European countries and analysed whether or not they are beneficial for research and archival purposes.

Although one of the rationales behind the GDPR was to harmonize their legal framework, in order to improve conditions for research and cross-border data flow this has not necessarily been the case. The GDPR has limited flexibility in its application. Nevertheless, the Regulation leaves room for national supplementary provisions, including derogations, and this possibility applies especially to the field of research. This represents both risks and opportunities. This report has described and compared national implementation of the GDPR with the focus on research in some specific countries, mainly Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany and Italy.

The team has selected the articles with highest relevance for research conditions in the legal framework. Thereafter the team has investigated if the countries mentioned above have had different interpretations and solutions – and if variations may influence conditions for research in general, data sharing and cross border research.

This report has compared the interpretation of the following articles from the GDPR:

- Lawfulness of processing – Art 6(1)(e)
- Processing of special categories of personal data – Art 9(2)(j)
- Appropriate safeguards - Article 89 (1)
- Processing of data relating to criminal convictions and offences – Article 10

The findings in this report show that some of the countries has implemented provisions in their national legislation that is beneficial for research, but some countries have not focused on research as a task in the public interest. In sum, the terms and conditions for processing personal data for research and archival reasons differ from one country to another.

The implications of these different interpretations in national legislations for research, will be further explored has the work of this task moves ahead.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Official
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

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1. Introduction

The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) has given European countries a unique opportunity to harmonize their legal framework, and to improve the conditions for research and cross-border data flow. The rationale behind the new regulation is indeed to ensure the same level of data protection throughout the EU in order to facilitate open access and reusability of research data. Thus, the GDPR has a limited flexibility in its application. Nevertheless, the Regulation leaves room for national supplementary provisions, including derogations, and this possibility applies especially to the field of research. This represents both risks and opportunities. This report will describe and compare national implementation of the GDPR with the focus on research in some specific countries, mainly Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany and Italy. Some of the information from the Nordic countries stems from a cross-border Nordic cooperation called the Nordic Network Project, where NSD was a leading partner.

This report has compared the national data protection legislations and analysed whether or not they are beneficial for research and archival purposes.

2. What has been done?

The project team has selected the provisions with highest relevance for research conditions in the legal framework. Thereafter this report investigates if the countries mentioned above have had different interpretations and solutions – and if variations may influence conditions for research in general, data sharing and cross border research. This report mainly compared the interpretation of the following articles from the GDPR:

- Lawfulness of processing – Art 6(1)(e)
- Processing of special categories of personal data – Art 9(2)(j)
- Appropriate safeguards - Article 89 (1)
- Processing of data relating to criminal convictions and offences – Article 10

3. A supplementary provision in the GDPR

Article 6 in the GDPR sets out conditions that must be met if you are to process ordinary categories of personal data lawfully. There are six available lawful bases for processing personal data. Which basis is most appropriate to use depends on the purpose of processing. This section of the report will further explore art. 6.1 (e) which is most appropriate to use for research purposes (besides consent art. 6.1 (a)). Art. 6.1 (e) states that you can process personal data if it is in the public interest.

The GDPR allows Member states to maintain or introduce more specific provisions when processing personal data for research or archival purposes in accordance with the legal basis “in the public interest” in Article 6.1(e). Article 6.2 states that public interest as lawful basis “may” be issued by Union or Member state law, thereby giving national legislators a margin for issuing national legislation for processing of personal data subject to Art. 6.1 (e)

“2. Member States may maintain or introduce more specific provisions to adapt the application of the rules of this Regulation with regard to processing for compliance with points (c) and (e) of paragraph 1 by determining more precisely specific requirements for the processing and other measures to ensure lawful and fair processing including for other specific processing situations as provided for in Chapter IX.”

The wording of the term “may” implies that the issuing of national provisions are optional. This interpretation is supported by the wording in Art. 9.2 (j), where the processing is preconditioned to be based on Member State law. However, there seems to be an inferred understanding, at least amongst most of the Nordic countries, that Art. 6.1(e) imposes the Member State to issue further legislation for the processing in the public interest. A summary of the opinions on this matter follows below:

The following paragraphs will discuss how the countries have interpreted the reference to these “more specific provisions”, cf. Art. 6.1 (e).

3.1 Sweden

The Swedish Data protection act (“Dataskyddlagen”) chapter 2, § 2 (1) determines a supplementary provision for processing data with the basis in Article 6. 1(e) when necessary to carry out a task in the public interest on the basis of formal law or other legal material, on the basis of a collective agreement, or a decision made on the basis of law/other legislative material.

The government leaves § 2, chapter 2 of the General Data Protection Act to fulfil the requirement of a national legal basis for processing of personal data for research purposes. According to the government, the term ‘laid down’ doesn’t require a specific provision for each processing, but rather that the task carried out in the public interest – the task to carry out research – must have a legal basis in national law. For private bodies, this requirement will be fulfilled if the project has been approved according to the Ethical Review Act. In order for research conducted by public authorities to be lawful, the national basis shall be laid down in national law, for example will research conducted by public universities and colleges be regarded as “laid down” in Högskolelagen (the College Act), or, if conducted by counties or municipalities acting as legal persons, when decided in accordance with the Municipality Act.

The Data protection Act of Sweden chapter 2, § 3 (1) states that the government can issue provisions/regulations allowing bodies not included by the archival laws can process data for archival purposes in the public interest.

Furthermore, paragraph two states that the government may decide that bodies as referenced in paragraph one may process personal data for archive purposes in the public interest in individual cases.

3.2 Finland

Finland passed a supplementary implementation act of the GDPR, the Data protection Act of Finland, which entered into force on January 1, 2019.

The act has two explicit legal bases for the processing of general personal data for research purposes, and for archival purposes in the public interest, in §§ 4.3 and 4.4. The provisions are based on Article 6.2 to clarify the application of the term processing of personal data “in the public interest” of Article 6.1 e). Both these legal bases include a test of proportionality and necessity.

3.3 Denmark

The Danish Data Protection Act § 6, states that personal data may be processed when the processing meets the requirements of Article 6.1 letters (a)-(f). The Act deliberates on the meaning of the wording in Art. 6.2 and 6.3, referring to “Union (...) or Member State law”, and decides that the Regulation does not impose issuing a specific statute for every processing. Thus, a statute allowing multiple processing’s for the fulfilment of a task in the public interest is deemed sufficient.¹ The conclusion seems to be that article 6 (1) e) is deemed to be directly applicable, as long as the controller is performing a task carried out in the public interest, or in the exercise of public authority. A national, implementing legal basis of the processing itself is, therefore, not required when processing personal data for the performance of a task in the public interest or in the exercise of public authority.

As for archival purposes, chapter 3, § 14, of the Danish Data Protection Act, states that personal data can be archived in accordance with the national archive legislation.

¹ *Betænkning 1565/2017* p. 132.

3.4 Norway

The Personal Data Act of Norway determines the need for national supplementary provisions when processing data pursuant to Article 6.1(e), referring to the provisions of Article 6.3 paragraph one. This results in § 8, paragraph one, stating that processing of personal data subject to Article 6.1 (e), is lawful if necessary, for historical and scientific research purposes, statistical purposes, or archival purposes in the public interest. Furthermore, § 8 refers to the duty to determine appropriate safeguards in accordance with Article 89.1.

3.5 Germany

From 25/05/2018, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the new Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG new) together ensure the protection of the fundamental right to informational self-determination in Germany. There are no explicit mentioning of Article 6.1 (e) in BDSG. This indicates that Germany has interpreted the issuing of a national provision as optional, and therefore has not issued further legislation for the processing of data in the public interest. There are however explicit mentions of the processing of special categories of personal data for research and archiving purposes without consent. One might draw the conclusion that one cannot process special categories of personal data without also processing ordinary categories of personal data. Furthermore, that research and archiving are in the public interest.

3.6 Italy

It is our understanding that in Italy there has not been a total repeal of the Privacy Code after the implementation of the GDPR. It is only the provisions contrary to the GDPR or that regulated matters already provided for by the GDPR has been revised. The Italian 2018 Budget Law (Law no. 205 of 27 December 2017) provides that data controllers which process personal data through automated means or “new technologies” on the basis of legitimate interest (art. 6. 1 (f)) shall send prior notification to the Italian Supervisory Authority and wait 15 days for its approval (before commencing processing). During the 15 days, the Supervisory Authority shall investigate and decide whether to approve, suspend or even to stop the processing where the legitimate interests of the data controller are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects.

This kind of provision does not seem to fall within the scope of discretionary power granted to Member States by the GDPR and, above all, the requirement for a prior check by the supervisory authority is at variance with the principle of accountability that characterizes the entire GDPR.

Article 6 affects Title V of Part II of the Italian Personal Data Protection Code (also known as the Italian Code of Privacy), which concerns the processing of personal data in the health sector. In the report accompanying the provision, it is emphasized that the new Articles actually reproduce substantially the current Articles of the Code: the changes are dictated by the need to update certain normative references and to expunge every

reference to the consent that, according to the regulation, no longer constitutes the only requirement of lawfulness (legal basis) of data processing. In relation to this part of the Code, Article 27 lists the numerous repealed Articles.

Table 1:

Processing of personal data “necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest”, Article 6.1(e).		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	The Data Protection Act, Chapter. 2, § 2(1). <i>When necessary to carry out a task in public interest based on legislative material, a collective agreement or a decision made based on legislative material.</i>	The Data Protection Act, Chapter 2, § 3 (1). <i>The government can issue regulations regarding data processing for archive purposes in the public interest.</i>
Finland	The Data protection Act, Chapter 2, § 4(3). Lawful processing when necessary for scientific/historic research and statistics, when proportionate to the execution of the public interest pursued.	The Data protection Act, Chapter 2, § 4(4). <i>Lawful processing if necessary, for archival purposes when proportionate to the execution of the public interest pursued and the rights of the data subject.</i>
Denmark	The Data Protection Act § 6. <i>Lawful processing if requirements of Art. 6.1 e) are met. The processing must have a legitimate foundation in one or several national legal bases. A specific legal basis for each processing is not required.</i>	The Data Protection Act, Chapter 3, § 14. <i>Processing allowed for archival purposes in accordance with national legislation.</i>
Norway	The Data Protection Act, § 8. <i>Processing lawful if necessary, for research and statistic purposes in the public interest. Appropriate safeguards in accordance with Art. 89.1 must be taken (see table 3).</i>	The Data Protection Act, § 8. <i>Processing lawful when necessary for archival purposes in the public interest. Appropriate safeguards in accordance with Art. 89.1 must be taken (see table 3).</i>
Germany	No supplementary provision in the BDSG. <i>However, the processing of special categories of personal data for research</i>	No supplementary provision in the BDSG. <i>However, the processing of special categories of personal data for archiving purposes, without consent, is</i>

	<i>purposes, without consent, is mentioned in section 27 in the BDSG.</i>	<i>mentioned in section 28 in the BDSG.</i>
Italy	<p>No supplementary provision in the Italian Personal Data Protection Code.</p> <p><i>However, it is clarified that consent is no longer the only legal basis for processing personal data.</i></p>	No supplementary provision in the Italian Personal Data Protection Code.

3.7 Summary

A significant part of the total amount of research conducted each year is conducted without consent, because consensual processing is impossible or disproportionately difficult. Thus, there is a need for a national legal basis that substitutes consensual research, i.e. the lawful processing of personal data “in the public interest”. To summarize, most of the European countries this report has examined so far have a national provision for the lawful processing of personal data for research purposes and archival purposes in the public interest. Both the Swedish, Finnish and Norwegian Data Protection Act ensure a clear legal basis for processing of personal data for these purposes. Denmark and Germany have not issued a similar provision in their respective national laws. However, as will be mentioned later in this report both Denmark and Germany have issued national legal basis for processing special categories of personal data. This indicates that research and archival purposes are indeed important in the public interest. As far as the project team knows the Italian law has not implemented a specific provision indicating that research/archival purposes are in the public interest but has clarified that consent is no longer the only legal basis for processing personal data.

A clear provision in national law stating that research is in the public interest, would make it easier for research institutions, as data controllers, to use 6.1 (e) as a legal basis, in cases where consent as a legal basis is not applicable.

4. Processing of special categories of personal data

Special categories of personal data are data that needs more protections because it is regarded as sensitive. In order to lawfully process special categories of personal data you need a lawful basis under art. 6 of the GDPR and a separate condition under art. 9. Processing of special categories of data is in principle prohibited but can be carried out if based on consent or other legal bases. Apart from consent, the most relevant legal basis for research and archival purposes is Article 9.2 (j). According to Recital 52, research serves as a basis for processing sensitive data only “when provided by Union or Member State law and subject to suitable safeguards.” The processing must, furthermore, be executed in accordance with Article 89. 1.

The following paragraphs give a short summary of the various implementations of national legal bases for the processing of personal data subject to Article 9.2 (j) in the European countries that is the focus of this report.

4.1 Sweden

The Swedish Data Protection Act has no paragraph stating that special categories of personal data can be processed for research purpose, in accordance with Art. 9 (2) j. However, The Swedish Data Protection Act chapter 3, § 3 (3) determines that authorities in correspondence with Art. 9 (2) g, may process sensitive personal data if necessary for important tasks in the public interest, and the processing don't involve an undue interference of the integrity of the data subject. The government has pointed out that this relates to public authorities, cf. Prop.2017/18:105 page 194.

The Swedish Data Protection Act chapter 3, § 4 states that the government may issue provisions regarding processing of special categories of data for fulfilling an "important public interest". The processing of special categories of personal data shall according to the Lagrådsremiss, be governed by the Ethical Review Act § 3, combined with § 6 of the same Act. The Ethical Review Act § 3 states that the act applies to research processing personal data covered by Art. 9 (1) or personal data mentioned in Art. 10. Paragraph 6 states the requirement of ethical approval for research.

The Lagrådsremiss page 87 states that ethical review of research projects are viewed as constituting a "suitable and specific measure", cf. Article 9.2 (j) for processing of special category of personal data for all research purposes, not only for the purpose of clinical drug research.² Moreover, the government regards approval according to the Ethical Review Act as a complementary national provision for research purposes in the public interest as required by Article 9.2 (j), cf. page 89 and paragraph 7.2.2 of the Lagrådsremiss. It is furthermore emphasized that the duty to submit the project to ethical review applies irrespectively of the legal basis. This results in a compulsory ethical review in both consents based and non-consent-based research studies.³

² Furthermore, it is stated that Ethical Review is a "suitable and specific" measure when processing personal data for research according to the Clinical Trial Regulation (536/2014).

³ The government does however, stress that the requirement for Ethical review only applies to special categories of personal data and personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, not ordinary personal data.

The Ethical Review Act §§ 7- 11a constitutes the requirements for lawful processing of special categories of personal data, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.

In the Data protection Act of Sweden. Chapter 3, § 6 it is stated that sensitive personal data may be processed for archival purposes in the public interest when necessary in order to follow regulations on the conservation and care of archives.

Furthermore, the government may issue regulations allowing other than those comprised by the archival laws to process sensitive personal data for archival purposes in the public interest.

4.2 Finland

The Data protection Act of Finland, §§ 6 (7) and 6 (8) states that sensitive personal data may be processed for scientific/historical research or statistics, and archival purposes in the public interest (except from genetic data) if specific and suitable measures. What is deemed to be suitable measures in Finland is mentioned in section 5.2 of this report when taking a closer look at safeguards in accordance with article 89.

4.3 Denmark

Paragraph 10, stk. 1 of The Data Protection Act states that personal data as mentioned in Art. 9 (1) may be processed for statistical or scientific investigations of significant importance for society, if necessary, for the conducting of these investigations. The appointment of a DPO is not made explicit in the Danish legislative text, but is, in the motives, considered as one possible safeguard in a wider “toolbox” of safeguards. Also, § 10, stk. 3 of the Danish Act states that data as mentioned in Articles 9 and 10 of the Regulation must not be disclosed to third parties without the approval of the supervisory authority, and that the authority may set conditions for the disclosing.

As in Sweden research project that process personal data has to be approved by an ethical committee, and also by the Danish Data Protection Authority.

As for archival purposes, *Betænkning 1565 part 1 – bind 2*, page 992, concludes that the current system – where processing for archival purposes is governed by the archival act, and The Data Protection Act governs the residual processing – can be continued.

4.4 Norway

The Personal Data Act § 9 states that special categories of personal data can be processed if necessary, for archival purposes, and for historical and scientific research purposes, as well as statistical purposes in the public interest, and the societal interest of the processing clearly exceeds the disadvantage imposed on the data subject. Furthermore, the processing shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, c.f. Article 89.1. In

addition to these preliminary conditions, § 9, paragraph two, instructs the controller to consult a data protection officer (or the like) prior to the processing, unless the controller has performed a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) in accordance with Article 35. Upon the consultation, the data protection officer shall assess whether the planned processing will fulfil the requirements of the Regulation and other provisions in national legislation. The duty to consult the data protection officer is regarded as a mean to ensure “suitable and specific measures”, cf. Article 9.2 (j). The duty also applies to consent-based research, cf. § 10. Other than this, the Ministry does not find it expedient to settle these kinds of measures in the law, on the grounds that each type of processing will require an individual assessment of what measures will be deemed “suitable and specific”.

4.5 Germany

Processing of special categories of personal data is mentioned in section 27 (1) “*Data processing for purposes of scientific or historical research and for statistical purposes*” of the BDSG. It is stated that processing of special categories of personal data as referred to in Article 9 (1) shall be permitted, also without consent for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, if such processing is necessary for these purposes. Furthermore, if the interests of the controller in processing substantially outweigh those of the data subject in not processing the data.

In addition to mentioning data processing for research purposes, Section 28 in the BDSG states that special categories of personal data can be processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, without consent.

When processing personal data for these purposes without consent, the data controller must take appropriate measures under BDSG Section 22(2) to protect the personal data, BDSG Section 27(1) implements GDPR Article 9(2) (j) in conjunction with GDPR Article 89(2). This is mentioned in more detail in section 5.5 of this report about article 89 and appropriate safeguards.

4.6 Italy

Italy established Italian current scheme of the legislative decree of harmonization. Article 2-sexies of decree, which refers to Article 9, paragraph 1, of the GDPR, sets specific conditions for the legitimate processing of particular categories of personal data, which are processed for reasons of significant public interest. More specifically, Article 2-sexies of the decree provides that the processing of the particular categories of personal data referred to in Article 9(1) of the GDPR, necessary for reasons of significant public interest, pursuant to the letter g), paragraph 2, of the same Article, are allowed if they are provided for by law of the European Union or, in the internal legal system, by provisions of law or, in the cases provided by the law, of regulation specifying the types of data that can be processed, the operations that can be carried out and the reason of significant public interest. It is important to remark that, pursuant to Article 2-sexies, paragraph 1, of the current decree, the provisions allowing the processing of such particular categories of personal data may be established, in the internal legal system, by primary or secondary sources of law.

Table 2:

The lawful processing of special (sensitive) categories of personal data for archival purposes in the public interest and for research purposes, Article 9.2(j)		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	<p>The Ethical Review Act, §§ 3 and 6. Also §§ 7- 11a.</p> <p><i>Ethical approval must be granted. Approval depends of the requirements for lawful processing of special categories of personal data, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.</i></p>	<p>In the Data protection Act, Chapter 3, § 6.</p> <p><i>When necessary in order to follow regulations on the conservation and care of archives.</i></p> <p><i>The government can make regulations allowing others to process for archival purposes in the public interest.</i></p>
Finland	<p>The Data protection Act, § 6 (7).</p> <p><i>May be processed for scientific/historical research or statistics. Demands necessary safeguards after § 6(2) number 1-11.</i></p>	<p>The Data protection Act, § 6 (8).</p> <p><i>May be processed for archival purposes in the public interest (except from genetic data). Demands necessary safeguards after § 6(2) number 1-11.</i></p>
Denmark	<p>The Data Protection Act, § 10.</p> <p><i>Lawful processing if necessary, for historical/scientific investigations of significant importance for society.</i></p>	<p>Regulated in archive laws.</p>
Norway	<p>The Data protection Act, § 9.</p> <p><i>May be processed for historical/scientific research and statistics in the public interest if proportionate, necessary, appropriate safeguards are met and consulted a DPO or performed a DPIA.</i></p>	<p>The Data protection Act, § 9.</p> <p><i>May be processed for historical/scientific research and statistics in the public interest if proportionate, necessary, appropriate safeguards are met and consulted a DPO or performed a DPIA.</i></p>
Germany	<p>The BDSG section 27 (1).</p> <p><i>Lawful processing for scientific or historical research purposes or statistics purposes, if proportionate and necessary. Necessary measures must be taken (see table 3)..</i></p>	<p>The BDSG section 28.</p> <p><i>Lawful for archive purposes in the public interest. Necessary measures must be taken (see table 3).</i></p>
Italy	<p><i>Processing might be lawful if specific conditions are met and a significant public</i></p>	<p><i>No supplementary provisions.</i></p>

	<i>interest. Provisions allowing the processing may be established in the internal legal system, by primary or secondary sources of law.</i>	
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4.7 Summary

Sweden has no explicit mention of research and archival purposes as a specific public interest for the processing of special categories of personal data. However, processing of personal data for research purposes has to be in accordance with the Ethical Review Act. In sum, the terms and conditions for processing sensitive personal data vary from one country to another, but the common denominator in most of the countries is the importance of ensuring that the processing of special categories of personal data is subject to adequate safeguards, c.f. Article 89.1. This is not surprising, seeing that Art. 9.2(j) explicitly refers directly to this article. It is also worth mentioning that the Italian and Danish legislator seems to demand a “significant” public interest, which might indicate a higher threshold using Art. 9. 2 (j) as a legal ground.

5. Appropriate safeguards pursuant to Article 89.1

As mentioned previously in this report, the processing of personal data may only take place on the condition that the safeguards of the Regulation are respected. In order to fulfil this prerequisite, the Regulation issues several provisions ensuring the lawful processing of data, for example, the principle of clarity, proportionality and necessity stated in Article 5 and Article 6. Other important aspects of ensuring the lawful processing of data are the provisions issued in Articles 24, 32 and 89. Together, these provisions make up a framework for ensuring the rights and freedoms of the data subject, with Article 89 being the most important provision regarding the processing of personal data for research purposes.

Article 89 is a new provision, in the sense that it has no equivalent in the 1995 Directive. Article 89.1 states that national or Union legislation should issue provisions for “appropriate safeguards” to ensure the basic rights and interests of the data subject. These safeguards shall ensure that “technical and organizational measures” are in place, particularly in order to ensure the principle of data minimization. According to the provision, these measures can include anonymization as the preferred safeguard, with pseudonymisation being the alternative solution. However, the preamble item 156 suggests that the safeguards pursuant to Article 89 are not exhaustive, and it is therefore assumed that the Union parties should issue national provisions to ensure safeguards. This perception is supported when reading Article 9.2(j) of the Regulations, which determines that the “[...]member State law [...] shall ... provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and interests of the data subject”, with reference to the demands of Article

89.1. The following paragraphs will give an overview as to how the countries in this report have chosen to interpret the requirement for these “appropriate safeguards” and “suitable and specific measures”.

5.1 Sweden

There is no mentioning in the Swedish Personal Data Act addressing what is deemed appropriate as safeguards. When it comes to the processing of personal data for research purposes, researchers need an ethical review (“etikprövning”), cf. the Act on Ethical Review (Etikprövningslagen). Apart from this, there are, to our findings, no specific safeguards stated. However, other Swedish laws that are outside the scope of this report may state suitable safeguards for processing of special categories of personal data, for research and archiving purposes.

5.2 Finland

The Data protection Act of Finland, §§ 6 (7) and 6 (8) states that sensitive personal data may be processed for scientific/historical research or statistics, and archival purposes in the public interest (except from genetic data) if specific and suitable measures. The measures are:

1. measures to being able to demonstrate who has registered, changed or disclosed personal data
2. measures to heighten the competence of personnel processing personal data
3. appointment of a DPO
4. the controller and processors internal measures to prevent the proliferation of personal data
5. pseudonymisation
6. encryption
7. measures to continuously ensure the confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of the processing systems and services relating to the processing of personal data, including the ability to restore availability and access to the data in a reasonable time in a physical or technical incident;
8. a procedure for periodically testing, investigating and evaluating the effectiveness of the technical and organizational measures to ensure the safety of the treatment,
9. special procedural rules to ensure that data protection and this law are observed when personal data is transferred or processed for any other purpose,
10. carrying out an impact assessment on data protection pursuant to Article 35 of the Regulation
11. other technical, procedural and organizational measures

5.3 Denmark

The Danish Personal Data Act has no specific reference to what should be considered as “appropriate safeguards” as stated in Article 89.1. Article 89.1 applies directly with no supplementary requirements regarding safeguards.

In the Danish proposal for the Personal Data Act (*Betænkning nr. 1565*) there was no in-depth discussion of various possible safeguards. In general, the proposal reproduces the demands stated in Article 89.1 (“technical and organizational measures”, “the principle of data minimization”, “pseudonymisation”).

5.4 Norway

The Norwegian Personal Data Act reiterates the duty to ensure “appropriate safeguards” in accordance with Article 89.1 in several provisions, hereunder §§ 8 and 9. In the motives, the Ministry of Justice states that neither the regulation itself, nor the preamble, gives clear guidance on the content of the requirements for safeguards, or for “suitable and specific measures”, other than entailing anonymization and/or pseudonymisation and provisions to ensure confidentiality (cf. Article 9.3). The Ministry assumes that the assessment of these safeguards/measures must be based on the duty to ensure that the processing is in accordance with the principles of article 5 and considering the sensitivity of the data and the risk associated with the processing, amongst other things. Other safeguards/measures might be prior consultation of the supervisory authority (Article 36) or a data protection officer (Article 37).

5.5 Germany

BDSG Section 22 (2) states that when processing special categories of personal data, without consent, appropriate and specific measures shall be taken to safeguard the interests of the data subject. Taking into account the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons posed by the processing, these measures may include in particular the following:

1. technical organizational measures to ensure that processing complies with Regulation (EU) 2016/679;
2. measures to ensure that it is subsequently possible to verify and establish whether and by whom personal data were input, altered or removed;
3. measures to increase awareness of staff involved in processing operations;
4. designation of a data protection officer;
5. restrictions on access to personal data within the controller and by processors;
6. the pseudonymization of personal data;
7. the encryption of personal data;
8. measures to ensure the ability, confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services related to the processing of personal data, including the ability to rapidly restore availability and access in the event of a physical or technical incident;
9. a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organizational measures for ensuring the security of the processing;

10. specific rules of procedure to ensure compliance with this Act and with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 in the event of transfer or processing for other purposes.

In addition, when processing special categories of personal data (without consent) for research purposes, data shall be anonymized as soon as the research purpose is fulfilled, unless this conflicts with legitimate interest of the data subject. Before de-identification, the data controller must separately store the characteristics enabling information to be associated with an identified or identifiable individual. The data controller may combine information only if required to fulfil the processing purpose, cf. BDSG, Section 27(3).

5.6 Italy

About the processing of special categories of data, with reference to biometric, genetic and health data, the Garante will issue, every two years, provisions on safeguard measures, aimed to identify "the security measures, like cryptography and pseudonymization procedures, minimization measures, specific methods of selective data access and to provide information to data subjects, as well as other necessary measures to guarantee the data subjects' rights."

It is our understanding that no such provisions yet are given by the Italian legislator. Article 89.1 therefore applies directly with no supplementary requirements regarding safeguards measures.

The mentioned provision will apply when processing biometric, genetic and health data. It remains to see if these safeguards measures also might be transferable when processing special categories of personal data in general.

Table 3:

Protecting the rights and freedoms of the data subjects when processing personal data for research purposes by considering appropriate safeguards pursuant to Article 89 (1).		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	<p>The Data Protection Act.</p> <p><i>No explicit regulation.</i></p> <p>The Ethical Review Act, §§ 7 – 11a.</p> <p><i>Constitutes the requirements for lawful processing of special categories of personal data.</i></p> <p><i>Ethical approval considered as constituting a “suitable and specific measure”.</i></p>	<p>The Data Protection act.</p> <p><i>No explicit regulation.</i></p>
Finland	<p>The Data protection Act, § 6 (2) number 1-11, cf. § 6 (1) number 7.</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in § 6 (2), 1-11.</i></p>	<p>The Data protection Act, § 6 (2) number 1-11, cf. § 6 (1) number 8.</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in § 6 (2), 1-11.</i></p>
Denmark	<p>The Data Protection Act.</p> <p><i>No explicit regulation.</i></p>	<p>Regulated in archive laws.</p>
Norway	<p>The Data Protection Act, §§ 8 and 9.</p> <p><i>Processing must be in accordance with art. 89.1. Concrete assessment in each case in light of the principles in Art.5. Researcher must consult with a DPO or performer a DPIA before processing special categories of personal data.</i></p>	<p>The Data Protection Act, §§ 8 and 9.</p> <p><i>Processing must be in accordance with art. 89.1. Concrete assessment in each case in light of the principles in Art.5. Researcher must consult with a DPO or performer a DPIA before processing special categories of personal data.</i></p>
Germany	<p>The BDSG Section 22 (2) and Section 27(3).</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in Section 22 (2). Necessary measures depends on a concrete assessment in each case.</i></p> <p><i>Main rule to anonymize special categories of</i></p>	<p>The BDSG Section 22 (2).</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in Section 22 (2). Necessary measures depends on a concrete assessment in each case.</i></p>

	<i>personal data when research purpose fulfilled, unless in conflict with interests of the data subject.</i>	
Italy	No explicit regulation yet. However, every second year it shall be given provisions on appropriate safeguards measures for processing biometric, genetic and health data.	No explicit regulation.

5.7 Summary

Two of the countries, such as Finland and Germany, have made comprehensive lists of what are specific and suitable measures. It is our understanding that also the Italian legislator soon will present a list of appropriate safeguard measures when processing biometric, genetic and health data. Norway on the other hand presupposes that safeguards are individually assessed by the controller for each processing, this is done by prior consulting with a DPO before processing. And Sweden sees an ethical review as a suitable measure. Denmark has not clarified in its national law what is considered to be appropriate safeguards. This indicates that solutions to assessing specific safeguards pursuant to Article 89. 1 are quite varied. A common understanding as to what measures will satisfy the requirement of appropriate measures (“suitable, specific, technical, organizational”) pursuant to Articles 89.1 and 9.2(j), would make sharing of research data across borders easier.

6. Processing personal data relating to criminal conviction and offences, cf. Article 10

The GDPR rules for special categories of personal data does not entail data about criminal allegations, proceedings or convictions. Processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences or related security measures based on Article 6.1 can only be carried out by official authorities or when the processing is authorized by Union or Member State law. According to the Regulation, supplementary legislation is required in order for national laws to allow the possibility of the processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences by others than official authorities.

6.1 Sweden

The Swedish General Data Protection Act chapter 3, § 8 determines that personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, can only be processed by an official authority.

Others than official authorities can process data relating to criminal convictions and offences, if the processing is necessary to obey provisions about archive.

In § 9 it is stated that the government may issue provisions deciding in what instances other controllers/processors than official authorities may process personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences.

The Ethical Review Act § 3 (2) states that the act also applies to research entailing processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences. The Ethical review applies regardless of whether the processing is carried out by public authorities, or not.

Approval according to the Ethical Review Act constitutes a legal basis for processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences for research purposes, cf. Ethical Review Act §3 (2) and § 6. As for personal data in Art. 9.1, §§ 7- 11a constitutes the requirements for lawful processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.

6.2 Finland

The Data protection Act of Finland, § 7.2 states that personal data subject to Article 10 may be processed for research purposes, cf. § 6 first paragraph, number 7, if the obligations mentioned in § 6 second paragraph are met.

There is no specific reference to § 6, first paragraph, number 8) (archiving of research material in the public interest). Still, processing for archival purposes can perhaps be lawful by the reference to § 6, first paragraph, number 2, which allows processing for performing a task governed by law.

6.3 Denmark

The Danish Personal Data Act states in § 10 (1) that information as mentioned in Article 9 and 10 can be processed if this is done solely in order to conduct statistical or scientific studies of significant societal importance and if processing is necessary for the sake of carrying out investigations. In § 10 (3), information may only be disclosed to third parties after prior authorization from a public authority. The authority may set further terms for the disclosure.

6.4 Norway

The Personal Data Act determines the need for a separate legal basis for research on personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, and states in the motives that there is in principle no good reason as to why these categories of personal data should be treated differently. The Personal data Act § 11 therefore

allows processing of these types of personal data for research purposes. Furthermore, the conditions of § 9 and 10 apply the same way. The ministry does, however, emphasize that § 11 is not a legal basis for processing of criminal offences-data. The controller must instead exhibit that the processing is lawful according to Article 6.1(e) and a supplementary legal basis in Union/Member State law (in Norway's case, § 8).

6.5 Germany

The BDSG does not contain a provision authorizing processing data about criminal convictions and offenses. However, other German laws that are outside the scope of this report may authorize processing this type of data. German law generally only permits public authorities to process this type of data.

6.6 Italy

It is our understanding the Italian legislator has not given an explicit provision authorizing processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offenses.

It is a national responsibility to regulate criminal matters, with regulations that are effective, proportionate and dissuasive. In this perspective, the Italian legislator has reviewed the criminal cases according to the Code regarding the protection of personal data, substantially confirming them, introducing the forecast of the damage as a characterizing element as an alternative to the profit purpose. Therefore, it is not held against the sole economic profit of the perpetrator of the offense but also of the damage caused to the interested parties, including the damage of the image and the reputation of the victim.

To limit the risk of overlaps between the administrative and criminal proceedings, a coordination mechanism has been inserted which provides that the Public Ministry informs the Control Authority without delay. In the same way, the Guarantor will be registered with the Public Ministry of the documentation collected in the administrative seat if a crime is presumed to exist.

Table 4:

Processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, cf. Article 10		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	The Ethical Review Act, §§ 3 (2) and 6. Also §§ 7- 11a. <i>Ethical approval must be granted. Approval depends of the requirements for lawful processing of data relating to criminal</i>	The Data Protection Act, Chapter 3, § 8. <i>Others than authorities may process if necessary, to obey archive provisions.</i>

	<i>convictions and offences, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.</i>	
Finland	The Data protection Act, § 7 (2), cf. § 6 (1) number 7. <i>May be processed for research purpose if obligations mentioned in § 6 (2) number 1-11 are met.</i>	The Data protection Act. <i>No explicit regulation. Perhaps allowed by § 7(2), cf. § 6 (1) number 2 if archiving is a task governed by law.</i>
Denmark	The Personal Data Protection Act, § 10. <i>Lawful processing if solely conducting statistical or scientific studies of significant social importance, and necessary to carry out investigations. Disclosing to third parties demands authorization from public authority.</i>	Regulated in archive laws.
Norway	The Personal Data Protection Act, § 11. Lawful processing for research purposes. Processing must be lawful according to art. 6.1 e) and the personal data protection act § 8. Condition in § 9 must be met.	The Personal Data Protection Act, § 11. Lawful processing for archiving purposes, Processing must be lawful according to art. 6.1 e) and the data protection act § 8. Condition in § 9 must be met.
Germany	No explicit regulation in the BDSG.	No explicit regulation in the BDSG.
Italy	No explicit regulation.	No explicit regulation.

6.7 Summary

Norway, Sweden, Denmark and Finland have a general provision relating to criminal convictions and offences which applies to research. Some countries require ethical review regardless of whether the processor is a public authority or not. The project team could not find any provision authorizing processing these kinds of data in the German laws. Furthermore, it is our understanding that the Italian legislator has not given an explicit provision authorizing processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences. As mentioned in 6.1 in this report, supplementary legislation is required in order for national laws to allow the possibility of the processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences by others than

official authorities. Therefore, it might be issues to share data across borders, if a data controller is subject to a nation without national regulation permitting processing of criminal convictions or offences.

List of Tables

Table 1: [Processing of personal data “necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest, Article 6.1 \(e\)](#)

Table 2: [The lawful processing of special \(sensitive\) categories of personal data for archival purposes in the public interest and for research purposes, Article 9.2 \(j\)](#)

Table 3: [Protecting the rights and freedoms of the data subject when processing personal data for research purposes by considering appropriate safeguards pursuant to Article 89 \(1\)](#)

Table 4: [Processing personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, cf. Article 10](#)